

Public summary of deliverable D2.8

RadicalZ aims to develop novel bio-based ingredients for markets such as nutraceuticals, cosmetics, and laundry products. Between month 30 and month 40, a total of 54 enzymes or engineered enzyme variants were selected for various applications. Of these, 34 enzymes are involved in the synthesis of bio-based prebiotics and glycosides, which hold potential for nutraceutical products. Two enzymes were selected for synthesizing ingredients from renewable resources for cosmetics, including moisturizers, wetting agents, antioxidants, and fragrances. Additionally, 15 enzymes were engineered for laundry products, specifically to reduce the release of synthetic fibers into wastewater and to create bio-based thickeners for liquid detergents.

The enzymes were sourced from public databases, partner collections, metagenome libraries, or commercial suppliers. Enzymes utilized in the RadicalZ project span 4 of the 7 enzyme commission classes and originate from all three domains of life. Out of the 54 enzyme candidates, 21 were engineered, with 20 of these being developed during the RadicalZ project. These enzymes have been screened and characterized using a variety of assays based on absorbance and fluorescence, along with chromatographic methods such as high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), gas chromatography (GC), and thin-layer chromatography (TLC).

